

Preventing The Criminal Tendencies Of Syrian Refugees Under Temporary Protection Status From The Perspective Of Migration Management

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Abstract

Hundreds of thousands of people lost their lives, suffered injuries, or fled Syria during the civil war process that erupted there in 2011 and continues to this day; it also decimated the nation's infrastructure. With its "Open Door Policy" and "Non-Return Policy," Turkey, which among all nations in the world receives the greatest number of Syrians, has turned into the port where millions of Syrians seek asylum. The impact of migration management and adaptation on reducing crime among Syrians with Temporary Protected status in Turkey is examined in this paper. Based on erroneous sources, there is a broad notion that the Syrian population in Turkey, whose numbers are growing quickly, is unable to adjust socially and

culturally to Turkey, engages in activities that disturb social peace, and has criminal tendencies.

Keywords: *Migration, Criminal Tendency, Temporary Protection Status*

Introduction

Migration, which has taken on various forms throughout history from antiquity to the present, is a dynamic process that begins with people moving to new places of residence by abandoning the routine they are accustomed to for a variety of reasons. This process shapes and alters the social, cultural, demographic, and economic conditions of societies. Migration affects numerous areas, including employment conditions, salary levels, issues integrating into a new community, and changes in behaviors and cognitive patterns. Migration has complex and diverse effects.

Turkey is one of the important countries in terms of migratory mobility, and due to its advantageous geopolitical location between Asia, Europe, and Africa, Turkey has occasionally served as both a transit country and a destination for migrants moving to other countries. Due to Turkey's unique geographic location, the developments in the global and regional arena have resulted in major shifts in the migrant and asylum-seeker flows.

Following 2014, Turkey became the nation that has absorbed the most asylum seekers and refugees in the world by widening its borders despite its own financial load. Turkey has not stayed indifferent to the humanitarian catastrophe of the Syrian civil war, which began in 2011 and is still ongoing today. Syrians who migrate to Turkey are not considered "refugees" under the Geneva Conventions. In the first period, Syrians who migrated to Turkey were classified as "guests," but because there is no international law equivalent to the term "guest" and because the civil war has not ended, Syrians, whose numbers have been steadily rising in Turkey, have been formally placed under "temporary protection." According to official statistics, the number of registered Syrians who have entered Turkey because of the Syrian

crisis—which has been called the most serious migration since the Second World War—has surpassed 3.7 million.

Syrians were first treated as guests by the Turkish population when they first arrived, but as it became evident that they would not be returning anytime soon because stability in Syria would not be established anytime soon, the locals started to emphasize the disparities between the two communities. This led to the development of the prejudice that asylum seekers disturb social order and peace, undermine public safety, and are likely to commit crimes, which was supported by unreliable sources.

The Concept Of Migration

The movement of people from one country, place, or location to another is defined as the phenomena of migration, which has been from the beginning of history and continues to be a significant idea today. This movement is motivated by economic, social, political, and cultural factors. The definition of the term "migration" is covered in several academic articles. According to nan, migration is an action that modifies the social, political, and economic fabric of society in addition to relocating the population geographically (Zer, 2004: 11). The term "migration," on the other hand, is defined more broadly by Erder as "any relocation activities within a certain period that may cause a rational distance and influence" (Erder, 1986: 9). According to Taurus, migration is the intentional or involuntary removal of people from their current habitats in terms of geography, social interactions, and economic opportunities to move to other environments (Toros, 2008:9). It is obvious that this issue will not be handled with a single point of view universally since it will not be feasible to make clear and exact assertions regarding migrant movements as in the formal sciences (Sinha, 1987: 23).

Although different authors have defined the concept of migration in different ways, it is generally understood to be the dynamic process brought about by the movement of people, which shapes the economic, social, cultural, and demographic circumstances of places as well as their development trajectory (Akıncı et al., 2015: 61). From the perspective of migrants, striving to fit into a new culture and society is a new creation process as a person or a society

without losing one's own identity by moving beyond the conventional cultural norms (Senol & Tastan, 2020: 484).

Far from being static, the nature and purpose of migration have evolved over time based on the people involved, the way societies are organized, the regions they live in, and the historical periods. Early in the history of humanity, migrations were driven by conflict, famine, and environmental factors, but throughout time, they began to be driven by political, economic, social, and cultural factors as well (Kara & Canan, 2015: 11). Migration that occurs within the borders of the same nation does not typically have significant or long-lasting effects, but external migration—also known as international migration—which happens when a "foreigner" enters the nation—may. Depending on the amount of newly arriving foreigners, their motivations for moving, and the circumstances of the nations they migrate to, external migration, which can happen in a variety of ways, may even evolve into a catastrophe (Bartram et al., 2017: 15).

Temporary Protection Status

No international agreement or international source contains a definition of the phrase temporary protection. Although it is not a novel form of international protection, the international literature does not yet define its legal foundation, content, scope, or borders (UNHCR, 2012: 1). To address the urgent requirement for protection, the phrase is now typically used to refer to temporary extraordinary protection in circumstances of mass inflow (Edwards, 2012: 596).

The goal of temporary protection, which is also a condition of the principle of non-refoulement, is to ensure that individuals who have left their country are protected in terms of their fundamental human rights by making sure they are placed in a safe environment as soon as possible (Çiçekli, 2014: 313). A kind of protection for people who are compelled to leave their country owing to factors including armed conflict, violent actions, human rights violations, and natural disasters is temporary protection, which has historically played a crucial role in international law (Fitzpatrick, 2016: 64).

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The legal framework for temporary protection under EU law was established by the European Council Decision of July 2001. Temporary protection is defined by the EU Directive as the provision of immediate and temporary protection to people in need, in the best interests of the people involved and others' protection, in the event of a mass asylum of people from third countries who are unable to return to their country of origin, who have been forced to leave their country, who have been displaced from their place of residence, or in the event of such a danger (<https://www.goc.gov.tr/avrupa-birligi>). 10.01.2023) Access.

According to the UNHCR's Global Trends Report, there were about nine million more displaced individuals in 2019 than there were in 2018, and there were 79.5 million more refugees and asylum seekers worldwide. (<https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/dunya/bmmyk-2019da-dunya-nufusunun-yuzde-1i-yerinden-edildi/1881143>). The majority of the 3.9 million Syrians who have been displaced abroad since 2014 have been housed in Turkey, according to UNHCR, making it the nation that has taken in the most displaced persons worldwide.

Temporary Protection Status Under Turkish Law

The LFIP has for the first time regulated the "temporary protection" status, which is to be supplied in situations of large influx into Turkey. In Chapter 3, Section 4 of the LFIP, temporary protection is governed differently from international protection statuses as follows: *“Temporary protection may be granted to foreigners who have been forced to leave their country, who are unable to return to the country from which they left, who arrive at or cross our borders en masse in search of urgent and temporary protection.”* (LFIP, Article 91)

The phrase "may be granted" in the law's article relates to the administration's latitude in this situation. Both a legal and political aspect of temporary protection exists. The same article's second paragraph states that a rule to be issued by the President of the Republic will govern the applications, processes, and guiding principles for temporary protection. The Syrians who fled their nation owing to the war after 2011 and came to Turkey are the most typical example of temporary protection in Turkey, which occasionally suffers large-scale migration due to its geographic location (Eksi, 2014: 164). The Syrians who entered Turkey through its doors were treated in accordance with the doctrine's fundamental guidelines for

temporary protection. Their basic needs were provided, the border gates were maintained open, and non-refoulement-compliant practices were implemented.

While the temporary protection regime adopted in Turkey does not specify a time limit, the EU Directive from the Council of the European Union in 2001 on the minimum criteria and norms for the granting of temporary protection sets a maximum duration of one year in a repeatable manner and a maximum of three years in total (Zenginkuzucu, 2018: 48-50).

Syrians Under Temporary Protection

It is not mentioned in the LFIP's Temporary Protected Status regulations that refugees and conditional refugees will face persecution or torture because of their religion, ethnic origin, membership in a certain social group, or political beliefs. The phrase "temporary protection may be provided to a group of people who have left their country in search of urgent and temporary protection and who are unable to return" is used here, in contrast to other international protection statuses, and the explanations for leaving their country are not given. It is argued that protection status is a sort of international protection that can only be offered in mass population migrations and cannot be used when coming individually.

The Arab movement quickly spread to numerous Arab countries, but not all the goals and expectations that it had at its inception were realized. In addition to Syria and its neighbors, the conflict that has been raging in the Syrian Arab Republic for almost ten years has had an impact on the region and the world. With its policy of open doors, Turkey, one of the war's most afflicted nations, has been the nation that has welcomed the most Syrian refugees. On April 29, 2011, a group of 252 people arrived at the Cilvegözü border gate to begin the first large exodus of Syrians escaping the war that had begun because of anti-regime rallies. This number steadily grew over time (Erdogan, 2016: 69). According to RA November 2021 data, there are 3 million 731 thousand 28 registered Syrians in Turkey who are receiving temporary protection.

Several definitions, including "refugee," "asylum seeker," and "individuals under temporary protection," were initially used for Syrians in addition to the definition of "guest,"

which has no equivalent in international law. It was initially believed that the influx of Syrian migrants was a temporary situation and that the asylum seekers would return to their countries once the war ended (Topal, 2015: 7). But each of these definitions has a unique connotation, and the number of Syrians migrating to Turkey has been rising over time. Syrians, whose numbers are continually growing but whose status in Turkey is unclear, have been temporarily placed under protection by Turkish officials.

The Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees ("CRSR") acknowledges social and economic rights for refugees, but it makes no provisions for extending these rights to foreigners who are temporarily protected from harm. The right to employment, health care, and education are among the rights that states are required to provide for in accordance with human rights, even though they have broad discretion to do so (Aslantürk & Tunç: 2018: 160).

Temporary Protection Regulation

The Temporary Protection Regulation went into effect in accordance with Article 91, paragraph 2 of the LFIP about six months after the LFIP's legislative foundation for temporary protection was formed. This closed a critical legal gap and clarified the status of Syrians (Official Gazette, 22.10.2014 P. 29153). The 1994 Regulation on Asylum was repealed when the TP Regulation went into effect. The Regulation governs the entrance to Turkey of people who may be eligible for temporary protection, as well as the methodology, length of their stay, processes, and guiding principles.

Benefit from Temporary Protection

The TPR, which is a crucial stage in creating the legal framework for temporary protection, introduces restrictive rules as well as comprehensive regulations, rights, and obligations for foreign nationals who will be granted protection.

The TPR, which has 63 articles and eleven chapters overall, defines temporary protection as follows:

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During this time of mass influx, it refers to the protection offered to foreign nationals who have been compelled to flee their country, who are unable to return, who arrive at or cross our borders in large groups or individually in order to seek urgent and temporary protection, and whose application for international protection cannot be evaluated individually. (TPR's Article 3/1 (f))

It is claimed that those who cross our borders on their own during the time of a major influx would also benefit from this protection, and this concept of temporary protection is a little more extensive than the description in the Law on Foreigners and International Protection. According to the tentative article in the Regulation's final section, starting on April 28, 2011, Turkey would offer temporary protection to anyone traveling from Syria. Also, it is specified that during the duration of temporary protection, requests for international protection would not be considered. In accordance with Article 8 of the Regulation, those who are not eligible for temporary protection are listed, and the appropriate authorities have the authority to remove the temporary protection of any such individuals.

The RA is the authorized institution for the procedures relating to people under temporary protection (Refugee Rights Center, "Temporary Protection in Turkey for Asylum Seekers Arriving from Syria," March 2017, p.3, <https://www.mhd.org.tr/images/yayinlar/MHM-1.pdf>). The RA conducts its activities in all provinces in Turkey working on migration (Access: 15.01.2023). Article 17/7 of the TPR states that those receiving temporary protection must first apply in person to their local governorates before being forwarded to a referral center. A temporary protection decision may be made by the President of the Republic on the recommendation of the Ministry if the requirements for temporary protection have been satisfied (Article 9/1 of the TPR). According to Article 9/2 of the TPR, the President of the Republic shall establish the fundamental guidelines and procedures, and authorized agencies and organizations shall carry out their execution.

Article 6 of the Regulation codifies Article 33 of the 1951 CRSR and the EU Directive's non-refoulement principle, guaranteeing that Syrians receiving temporary protection won't be sent back to Syria unless they voluntarily do so.

Rights and obligations of foreigners under temporary protection

Foreign nationals who want temporary protection must first finish the registration process by getting in touch with the appropriate Turkish institutions. Foreigners who are required to pre-register will each receive a "Temporary Protection Identity Document" if their pre-registration assessment is good. The identification document for temporary protection is governed by Article 25 of the Regulation. The relevant provision states that neither the identity document nor any other document that replaces a residence permit under the LFIP confers the ability to seek for Turkish citizenship. Foreigners who possess these temporary identity certificates are entitled to safe shelter in Turkey and may take advantage of the facilities offered to individuals receiving temporary protection.

The sixth section of the law, titled "Services to be given to Temporarily Protected People," which is located between Articles 26 and 32, contains the rules governing the services that must be offered to registered foreigners. While the regulation specifically regulates health, education, employment opportunities, social services, and interpreting services, additional services not covered by the regulation will be given to the same extent as public institutions' facilities (Article 26 of the TPR). 139 As a result, persons receiving temporary protection have access to many of the rights afforded to refugees with a service understanding (Aslantürk & Tunç, 2018: 143).

The Regulation's Article 29 lays out the policies and guidelines for hiring people with temporary protection. For Syrians receiving temporary protection, it is crucial that they are able to support themselves independently, eliminate unregistered labor, and have access to legitimate employment opportunities. The "Regulation on Work Permits for Foreigners Under Temporary Protection" (hereafter referred to as "RWPTP") was adopted on January 15, 2016 (Official Gazette, January 15, 2016, p. 29594). The RWPTP's first item declares that its goal is to establish the policies and guidelines for the temporary work status of foreigners. According to Article 5, a work permit application may be submitted to the competent ministry six months following the start date of temporary protection. The RWPTP intends to formally register Syrians living in Turkey illegally in addition to easing Syrians' access to the job market (Kara & Canan, 2016: 154).

The seventh part of the TPR states under the heading "Obligations" that temporary protected persons are required to abide by the laws and administrative procedures generally as well as the procedures that are specific to them in Turkey.

Termination of Temporary Protection Status

In Articles 11 and 12 of the TPR, the termination of temporary protection is governed in a binary fashion. Individual temporary protection expiration is governed by Article 12, while group end of temporary protection is governed by Article 11.

According to Article 11 of the TPR, the President of the Republic must accept a proposal from the Ministry of Interior to end temporary protection, and the President must then issue a resolution to that effect. The President of the Republic may decide to allow temporary protected persons to return to their home countries, to consider each application for international protection, or, if the circumstances are suitable, to permit temporary protected persons to remain in Turkey with the resolution to terminate protection. As can be seen, it is not conceivable for the temporary protection status to be permanently removed and for these individuals to be returned to their countries in the event that the crisis in the nations of the temporarily protected persons ends. Depending on the situation, individuals might be permitted to remain in Turkey even if temporary protection is terminated by the President.

The individual termination or revocation of temporary protection is governed by Article 12 of the TPR. If a person receiving temporary protection leaves Turkey voluntarily, is awarded protection by another nation, departs for a third country, or passes away, the protection is discontinued individually. If a person receiving temporary protection becomes a citizen of Turkey, temporary protection will likewise terminate for that person specifically. If the status of persons who do not fit the requirements for temporary protection is later revealed, the RA or the governorships will rescind temporary protection.

According to TPR Article 15, in the event of circumstances that could endanger the nation's national security, public order, or public health, the President of the Republic may opt to restrict temporary protective measures or decide to suspend them temporarily or permanently.

Relationship Of Syrians Under Temporary Protection With Crime

Syrians would migrate to Turkey for a considerable amount of time as the civil war extended across the country and proved to be unwinnable. Turkish society and politicians have recognized that the issue of integrating visitors to Turkey requires attention from all angles, including social, political, and economic ones, to ensure the harmonious integration of two main societies (Znay, 2019: 1). There are many complex adaptation issues between the two civilizations because of asylum seekers' intentions to uphold the customs, traditions, and stereotyped behaviors they have developed in the previous countries they have lived in. The issues resulting from the failure to ensure healthy integration between the two societies contribute to the perception of asylum seekers as foreigners, criminals who disturb social order and social peace, who engage in illegal activities, and who foster prejudice in the local society during this process of increasing social mobility.

Considering the official studies and statistical information shared in this study on the crime rates of Syrian asylum seekers, it is clear that the way Syrians are depicted in some media outlets—as people who commit crimes and beg—and who are frequently mentioned in violent and negative news stories is the result of a biased viewpoint. In general, the incidence of judicial events involving Syrians in occurrences in general is not high and has been declining over time, according to a review of the official statistics given by the Ministry of Interior.

Various Data and Analyzes on the Criminality Levels of Syrians

There is a widespread belief among local communities across the world that immigrants are more likely to commit crimes than native-born citizens and that migrants commit most crimes. This impression may lead to high tensions in the areas where migrants dwell because of the crimes they commit (Güçlüten & Cereci, 2021: 26).

Local research on the effect of Syrians on occurrences of public order in Turkey has also produced data showing that locals blame Syrians for the crime rates. Is it true that Syrians increase the crime rate? was a question that Hakan Memis asked locals in Kilis. Of those interviewed, 77.5% said "yes," 14.5% said they were unsure, and just 8% said "no." (Memis,

2015: 106). Coskun Tastan and his colleagues conducted a face-to-face interview with 400 people in Ankara, and the findings are as follows: 62% of respondents indicated that there had been an increase in theft cases following the arrival of Syrians, and 60% indicated that there had been an increase in violence, assault, killing, and wounding incidents.

The number of Syrians who engage in or commit crime is minimal, and some of the crimes they commit are as a result of events that happen in their own neighborhood. The perception is incorrect; contrary to popular belief, the crime rate involving Syrians is quite low, according to T24 on October 15, 2018, <https://t24.com.tr/haber/algı-yanlıs-sanıldiginin-aksine-suriyeliler-karistigi-suc-orani-oldukca-dusuk,723457> (accessed on January 13, 2023). Locals, on the other hand, believe that security issues have worse. The totals and percentages of some of the crimes committed by Syrians in the criminal court files submitted in 2020, which resulted in significant security issues that the society is concerned about, are presented separately for individuals with Turkish nationality and individuals with foreign nationality. This unrealistic perception is based on false and unreliable sources. Around 95% of the crime files from the portion that makes up 1.0% and above of the crime files submitted with the criminal courts in 2020 were used to create this list of crimes. When the tables are examined, it becomes clear that there are not a lot of criminal cases brought before Turkish courts that are allegedly perpetrated by foreigners. The following conclusions may be drawn from the data about the three offences with the greatest rate among the criminal court files submitted in 2020:

- *In 2020, crimes against property accounted for the highest proportion of the files filed with the criminal courts with 21.9%. In 2020, 3.1% of all crimes against property files filed nationwide were committed or alleged to have been committed by foreigners. In 2020, the number of crimes against property cases filed in criminal courts for foreign individuals was calculated as 0.24% of the foreign population of approximately 6 million¹⁷¹ (Migration Data Portal, “TURKEY Key Migration Statistics,” https://www.migrationdataportal.org/data?cm49=792&focus=profile&i=stock_abs_&t=2020 Access: 14.01.2023).*

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- In 2020, crimes against bodily integrity accounted for the second highest proportion of the files filed with the criminal courts with 21.5%. In 2020, 2.2% of all crime files filed against bodily integrity across the country of crime files committed or alleged to have been committed by foreigners. In 2020, the number of crimes against bodily integrity files filed in criminal courts for foreign individuals was calculated as 0.17% of the foreign population of approximately 6 million.
- In 2020, crimes against liberty accounted for the third highest proportion of the files filed with the criminal courts with 14.6%. In 2020, 2.1% of all crimes against liberty files opened nationwide were committed or alleged to have been committed by foreigners. In 2020, the number of crimes against liberty files filed in criminal courts for foreign individuals was calculated as 0.11% of the foreign population of approximately 6 million.
- Looking at the gender distribution of the criminal files opened for foreigners, approximately 85% are men and approximately 14% are women. Of the 3.7 million Syrian population in Turkey, the vast majority, 2.5 million, approximately 67%, are women and children aged fourteen and under.

Table 1. Defendants by nationality in cases in Criminal Courts during the year

YEARS	EN NATIONAL	FOREIGNER	GENERAL TOTAL
2010	2 358 805	20 384	2 391 747
2015	1 998 891	34 592	2 041 058
2020	1 635 968	53 052	1 708 660

Source: Compiled from the data of the General Directorate of Judicial Registry and Statistics.

The distribution of defendants in criminal courts by nationality is shown in Table 1 above for certain years. The percentage of foreigners in Turkey increased from 1.9% of the total population in 2010 to 5.5% of the total population in 2015. The percentage of foreigners to the overall population was 7.2% in 2020. Turkey Important Migration Statistics, Migration

Data Portal, <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/data?cm49=792&focus=profile&i=stockabs&t=2020>, accessed 15.01.2023.

- *The percentage of criminal cases in Turkey that included foreigners in 2010 was 0.85%. Due to the absence of a Syrian civil war in 2010, there was no significant influx of Syrians into Turkey.*
- *In 2015, 2% of all criminal cases in the nation included accusations against foreign people. 5.5% of the overall population was made up of foreigners in the nation in 2015. The government said that 2,255,299 Syrians were living legally in Turkey as of the beginning of 2016. Criminal cases involving foreigners in 2015 did not significantly affect criminal cases in the nation (Posta, "Here in Turkey last number of registered Syrians," 13.01.2016. <https://www.posta.com.tr/iste-turkiyedeki-son-kayitli-suriyeli-sayisi-ocak-2016-321871>, Access: 15.01.2023). This includes the over 2 million Syrians who sought refuge in Turkey with the massive Syrian migration that*
- *In 2020, 3% of all criminal cases in the nation included defendants who were foreign nationals.*
- *For the last ten years, the percentage of foreigners living in Turkey has continuously risen, and as of 2020, it has surpassed 7%. The statistics data show that even if the foreign population, which is mostly made up of Syrian asylum seekers, has continuously grown over the years, criminal cases involving foreign people as defendants have not significantly changed the percentage of criminal cases across the nation.*

Although if there are misconceptions in the local community that immigrants from other countries are likely to commit crimes, the proportion of instances in which they are charged in court is minimal, despite the years' fast growth in the number of foreign residents. It is clear that immigration cannot be directly linked to crime when the statistical data of the instances in which immigrants of various nations entering Turkey are defendants are analyzed. The country's crime rates have not risen concurrently with the country's exponential expansion in the number of foreign residents over the last ten years, and this has not significantly affected instances of public order in the nation.

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The distribution of people arriving at the Prison and Execution Institute in 2020 is shown in Table 2 below, broken down by nationality.

Table 2. Distribution by Nationality

	2014	2016	2018	2020
EN National	98.2	97.8	96.8	96.2
foreigner	1.8	2.2	3.2	3.8

Source: Obtained from Turkish Statistical Institute's data.

The distribution of those sent to prisons and execution facilities in 2014, 2016, 2018, and 2020 is shown in the table above, broken down by nationality. From 2014 and 2020, there was a 2% rise in the percentage of foreign nationals in the nation's prison and execution facilities. The percentage of crimes committed in Turkey has not changed dramatically despite the continual growth in the number of foreign nationals, especially Syrians. The information on criminal files submitted to the criminal court in 2020 shows that the number of security events involving foreign nationals is not as great as expected conceptions.

In Turkey, where there are more than 6 million foreigners, there are more over 3.7 million registered Syrians, according to statistics from November 2021. Around 61% of all foreign residents are Syrian. The Ministry of Interior released the information on occurrences involving Syrians and public order that was described above. Although the most current research data given by the Ministry of Interior is from 2019 and the rate reported in 2019 is 0.8%, a 2013 study found that the incidence of security incidents involving Syrians was 2.8%.

Figure 1 The Ratio of Public Order Incidents Involving Syrians to Total Public Order Incidents in Turkey.

Source: Compiled from Ministry of Interior data.

Even though the number of Syrians entering Turkey has increased over time and now stands at millions, the proportion of security incidents involving Syrians to all incidents involving public order in Turkey has decreased, which can be attributed to adaptation programs implemented throughout Turkey in a variety of fields.

Turkish citizens have the false impression that Syrians disturb public order and security. Research reveals that whereas Turks often sue Syrians, the frequency of Syrians becoming involved in legal issues is quite low. Provocative security risks associated with this view might eventually turn the two groups against one another (Tunca, 2018: 63-64). The statistics on the participation of Syrians in crime are at low levels, not even surpassing 3%, when the data presented according to the number of Syrians in Turkey is examined.

There are often inflated and erroneous news headlines regarding criminal situations involving Syrians in Turkish print and visual media. These sensationalized and unfounded news reports have a significant impact on local perceptions of immigrants as being mostly criminals and produce tensions, disputes, and antagonistic inclinations between the two

populations (Kz maz, 2018: 394). Analysis of the data demonstrates that migration and crime cannot be directly linked in a good way. Given that more than 6 million criminal cases involving foreign nationals were filed in Turkey in 2020, it would be unfair to claim that immigration alone is having a growing impact on crime rates. The propensity of migrants to commit crimes is brought on by a variety of reasons.

Factors Triggering the Crime Tendency of Syrian Refugees

Several studies have shown that migration raises crime rates or that high rates of arrest, conviction, and incarceration among select migrant populations in specific locations and at specific periods are related to various factors (Kizmaz, 2018: 405).

There are several factors that influence immigrants' participation in the commission of crime. An examination of these variables shows that the criminal tendency of immigrants is influenced by a variety of factors, including personal characteristics, social adjustment issues, financial considerations, poor educational attainment, and bad media coverage. According to the paper written by Orhan and Gündogar, which investigates the consequences of Syrian refugee seekers on Turkey, the harsh qualities of the area where asylum seekers dwell may provide the groundwork for conditions that are conducive to crime and violence. The young population of asylum seekers who have low educational or income levels, who are unable to support themselves, who feel excluded and unwelcome in society, may in the long run be a part of security and public order incidents and may be a source of many crimes, according to Orhan and Gündogar (2015: 19–20).

According to estimates, the majority of Syrians who fled their homes and moved to Turkey in search of a safer place to live would continue to do so even when their country's conflict comes to an end. In addition to the many issues that await them in the new countries where they settle, the effective integration of Syrians—who are seen as aliens, peacebreakers, and beggars by the locals—is crucial for public safety. It should be taken into account that the difficulties Syrians living outside of the camps have integrating into Turkish society could lead to serious issues between them and the locals, increase the likelihood that they will get involved in terrorist activities and illegal trade in Turkey, and make them extras in security incidents (Korkmaz, 2016: 94).

The process of migration results in an expansion and variety of requirements, and the worries brought on by financial difficulties promote social unrest and surroundings that reflect the criminal tendency that is ingrained in human structures (Demir, 2011: 71). The majority of Syrians living in Turkey's cities are criminal by nature for a variety of reasons. First off, a number of causes are listed as contributing to Syrians' criminal prejudice, including the economy, unemployment, lack of education and job-seeking abilities, personal motivations, issues with socio-cultural adaption, and media bias.

Effects of Individual Characteristics

Millions of people are now migrating to Turkey, and this number now has an impact on the whole community. As a result of the massive influx of Syrians, individuals of all ages have been allowed entry into the nation without restriction, and a large portion of this population is made up of children and young Syrians. The age status of individuals coming in the nation is not specifically addressed in Turkey's fundamental legal texts on foreigners' legislation, and it is stated that if the foreigner is a kid, the process that applies to the adult accompanying the foreigner will be applied to the child.

Over 1.7 million of the more than 3.7 million Syrian refugees who are officially registered and residing in Turkey are youngsters between the ages of 0 and 18. There are around 1.9 million young Syrians between the ages of 18 and 65, while 40,000 Syrians are above the age of 65.

More than half of the Syrian population in Turkey is youthful and middle-aged, and Turkey has taken in the most Syrians worldwide since 2014. Syrians in childhood, adolescence, and youth between the ages of 0 and 18 make up about half of the remaining population.

During the Second World War, it was found that young people were breaking the law more often, and that the incidence of delinquency had grown. These developments had a significant negative influence on society. Delinquency is the outcome of all the bad impacts that develop psychologically, cognitively, familiarly, and socially, according to studies on

juvenile offenders (Yörükoglu, 2000: 301). Immigrants are compelled to acquire new habits or may have a tendency toward certain undesirable behaviors when they leave their old social context and join a new one with different dynamics. In their new social setting, one of these behaviors may be crime (Delice & Yasar, 2014: 3).

According to the gender breakdown of criminal files opened for foreigners in 2020, male foreigners accounted for around 85% of files opened in the reference year, while female foreigners accounted for approximately 14% of files opened. 2.5 million of the 3.7 million Syrians living in Turkey are children or women under the age of fourteen. Young Syrian males make up the great bulk of the surviving population. Studies show that a migrant's age, gender, education level, and traumatic experiences all have a role in whether they get involved in criminal activity. Studies show that the propensity to commit crimes grows with age, particularly in-migrant communities where the proportion of young people is large (Kizmaz, 2018: 405). The reality of "lonely young males" with the potential to pose significant hazards is shown by the fact that the Syrian community in Turkey has more male adults between the ages of 15 and 39 than female adults (Tunca, 2018: 52). It has been shown that young people's crimes, the most of whom reside in cities, have risen and varied through time and have become a severe issue that impacts society, particularly with the development in industrialization after the second half of the twentieth century. But, it is wrong to denigrate young foreign males and paint them as aggressive, prospective criminals who are likely to commit crimes. Young immigrants face several challenges in the new countries they move to. Foreign young people should be integrated in lifelong learning and adaptation programs in the communities where they settle, educated to respect local cultural norms, and programs for the two civilizations' secure coexistence should be implemented.

Education Impact

Children and students will be able to break their relationships with unhealthy settings if they can attend a suitable school and obtain the necessary education. They will also be able to mature in accordance with the laws that are enforced. For instance, a research carried out in

the United States discovered that juvenile criminal activity rose on days when schools were closed (Dönmezer, 1994: 286).

Although just 60,000 Syrians reside in shelter facilities in Turkey, 98% of the country's population is dispersed throughout 81 regions. Thousands of Syrian youngsters have transitioned from childhood to adulthood in the 10 years since Syrians first came in Turkey. Hundreds of thousands of Syrians will be growing up in Turkey over the next years since it is unclear when the civil conflict will finish, and Syria will once again be a safe place to live. For their future possibilities, welfare, and the maintenance of social stability, these hundreds of thousands of Syrians must move into adulthood with the appropriate credentials. Children and teenagers who are unable to attend school will first lose hope for the future, become ghettoized and politicized, and societal instability and crises will manifest (Tastan & Çelik, 2017: 62).

77% of Syrians are under the age of 35, with a gender split of 53.7% males to 46.2% women, and a percentage of 20% young people between the ages of 15 and 24. Between the ages of 5 and 17, 32% of Syrian children and adolescents are in the educational stage. The MoNE reported that 64.22% of children of school age, or almost one-third of the registered Syrian population, were enrolled in school in the academic year 2020–2021.

Table 3. *Schooling Rates of Syrian Population Under Temporary Protection in Turkey by Years*

Education Period	Registered Syrian Child Population Aged 5-17	Syrian Students Accessing Education	Schooling Rate %
2014-2015	756.000	230.000	40,91
2015-2016	834.842	311.259	59,09
2016-2017	833.039	492.544	59
2017-2018	972.200	610.278	62,52
2018-2019	1.047.536	641.058	61,39
2019-2020	1.082.172	686.581	63,23
2020-2021	1.197.124	768.839	64,22

Source: Compiled from Ministry of National Education data.

There has been a yearly rise in the number of Syrian children and teenagers who are being given temporary refuge in Turkey by the Turkish government. In the meanwhile, Turkey is actively engaging in the execution of programs and research to guarantee that people in Syria have access to educational opportunities. In 2014, there was a marked decrease in the likelihood that Syrians would go back to their country soon, but at the same time, the number of Syrians entering Turkey surged dramatically. As a direct reaction, the Ministry of National Education (MoNE) launched efforts to develop lasting and revolutionary solutions for the incorporation of Syrians into the educational system. Education activities, which had been carried out in makeshift ways, were systematized, and new plans and policies were quickly implemented and implemented by mobilizing state-owned physical facilities such as classrooms, fixtures, and human resources such as teachers and administrators. This was done by systematizing the education activities (Tastan and Steel, 2017: 65). The percentage of Syrian children who had access to education rose from 40.91 percent in the academic year 2014-2015 to 64.22 percent in the academic year 2020-2021 in Turkey. This

indicates that the number of Syrian students who are able to receive an education in Turkey has been steadily growing over the years.

According to the data that is now available on the general education level of the Syrian population in Turkey, the schooling rate of Syrian children today has grown by more than twenty-four percent in comparison to the years in which they first began to migrate to Turkey. It is of the utmost significance that children and young people in Syria take an active role in their education and training, not only for their own futures but also for the sake of maintaining societal cohesion. In particular, the education of Syrian children is of the utmost importance for a common life in social cohesion in a safe and dignified manner by integrating with the values and culture of the society in which they are guests. This can be accomplished through education that teaches the children about the values and culture of the society in which they are guests. Children in Syria who have had the opportunity to participate in the educational system of the society in which they live as part of the schooling process will have a better chance of improving their own personal development and future welfare, as well as overcoming the difficulties that arise during the process of social adaptation in a manner that is both simpler and more practically applicable. Individuals who are able to receive an education while they are in Turkey will, in the long run, be in a position to contribute to the economy and social life of Turkey, while those who are able to return to Syria will be in a position to play important roles in the reconstruction of their country as a result of the education they have received.

Children in Turkey who are unable to access their constitutionally guaranteed right to education and training and who are therefore unable to attend school may expose themselves to a number of dangers. Many people are concerned that the masses of ignorant people will one day become a lost generation, and that their tendency toward radicalism will grow. Those children and young people who are not given the opportunity to obtain an education and who are unable to receive an education of a sufficient quality will be coerced into working as cheap labor in occupations where they are the only ones who can do the job. The process of integration will be challenging for both parties because young people, whose expectations for the future have been dashed, will find it challenging to integrate with the local society in the

new places they have migrated to because they are unable to establish sufficient ties with the local community. This will make the process challenging for both parties. Taking into account the fact that children who are not educated are more likely to come from families with a low financial income level, it is important to recognize that the lack of predictability in these children's futures may increase their propensity toward criminal behavior, as well as the number of early marriages, drug addiction, and the possibility of becoming a member of criminal organizations. This is because it prevents these children from developing a sense of belonging to the society in which they are raised.

Adult asylum-seekers from Syria who are now living in Turkey should be given the opportunity to improve their professional skills and get instruction in the Turkish language for them to be able to develop and sustain an atmosphere that is harmonious with Turkish society. Because of difficulties in acquiring languages and obtaining occupational training, most Syrians will continue to struggle with unemployment and poverty, preventing them from achieving social empowerment. If vocational training and language classes are not able to live up to the needs and demands of the Syrian people, this may result in problems that make it impossible for Syrians to manage their own affairs, contribute to the economy of their households, and make certain plans for the future. It is imperative, in order to support asylum seekers in making a self-sustainable start in the long term and to prevent the persistence of the poverty problem, to create the necessary infrastructure, develop training services, and employ relevant staff by making use of international funds and support. In order to do this, it is essential to create the necessary infrastructure, develop training services, and employ relevant staff (Duman, 2019: 362).

Economic Causes and Employment Problem

Poverty, a low-income level, and unemployment all have a direct relationship to the violence and crime episodes that are regularly encountered in cities, and these three factors feed off of each other in a spiraling pattern of cause and effect (Akalin, 2016: 8). A substantial amount of study has been carried out in sociological and criminological studies, particularly to identify the nature of the link that exists between unemployment and the various crime characteristics (Kizmaz, 2003: 282).

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Despite the small number of research that have been carried out in Turkey on the topic, a significant number of studies have been carried out in other countries on how economic factors are related to criminal activity. Becker (1968) and Ehrlich (1973), who were the first scholars to investigate the connection between economic circumstances and criminal behavior, arrived at several results based on the presumption that conditions in the labor market had an effect on criminal behavior. According to this hypothesis, when there are few chances available in the job market, people may resort to engaging in illicit activities since they are seen as a replacement for those alternatives. According to the findings of the survey, one of the reasons people turn to illicit activities is to supplement their income. The individual who is without a job evaluates the income that can be earned in the labor market in comparison to the income that can be earned from engaging in illegal activities, considering the possibility that they will be caught and punished, and then makes a decision in this direction as a result. After finishing their research, Becker and Ehrlich concluded that there is a correlation between high unemployment and high crime rates, but there is an inverse correlation between high earnings and high crime rates (Pazarlioglu & Turgutlu, 2007: 64).

According to the findings of a research that was carried out by Piopiunik and Ruhose, the influence of migration on crime rates seems to be especially prominent in areas that have high rates of both unemployment and crime. It was shown that major determinants in migrants' engagement in criminal activity include their age group, particularly the age range of 15 to 25, their level of education, professional skills, language competence, and restricted and low level of entrance into the labor market (Piopiunik & Ruhose, 2017: 258-259). Yet, there is no general agreement among academics on this topic at present time even though studies on how crime is impacted by economic situations have been continuing up until now. The conventional wisdom is that there is a causal relationship between unemployment and criminal behavior, and that there is a correlation between the level of unemployment and an increase in the number of crimes committed (Soroka & Bryjak, 1995: 262).

At this time ten years ago, Syrians began migrating to Turkey. At first, they lived in camps, but shortly after, they started settling in cities in a dispersed fashion. Some of them still live in camps. Since they were unable to locate consistent and ongoing help, they joined

the labor market illegally to make revenue for themselves and any families that they may have. As the number of Syrians working illegally in Turkey as low-wage labor was estimated to be in the hundreds of thousands, in 2016 the state of Turkey passed the Regulation on Work Permits for Foreigners under Temporary Protection in order to make it possible for asylum seekers to legally find employment in Turkey. At this phase, which gives them the ability to work legally, it is regulated that Syrians who are under temporary protection may apply to the relevant units for a work permit as soon as they are registered, and they will get a response within a short period of time. "Number of Syrians in Turkey March 2021," Refugees Association, 10.04.2021. <https://multeciler.org.tr/turkiyedeki-suriyeli-sayisi/>, Accessed: 16.01.2023. According to the most recent data that was made public by the Ministry of Family, Labor and Social Services on March 31, 2019, the number of Syrians who were granted work permits in Turkey was determined to be 31,185.

According to the findings of the research titled "Syrians Barometer- 2019: Framework for Living in Harmony," which was conducted in 2014 and 2017 with the support of the Turkish-German University Center for Migration and Integration Studies (TAGU) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and published for the third time, 38.7% of Syrians over the age of 12 in 2017 and 37.9% in 2019 were employed. The research was prepared in 2014 and 2017 with the support of the Turkish-German University According to the "Syrians Barometer-2019 Announced," published by the Asylum and Migration Research Center on September 9, 2020 (<https://igamder.org/TR/-suriyeliler-barometer-2019-announced>), the topic of "working conditions" is the one in which Syrians in Turkey face the greatest challenges and voice the most complaints. Obtainable at: 15.01.2023).

Most working Syrians are engaged in low-paying and deplorable circumstances in the construction, manufacturing, heavy industrial, textile, and commerce sectors. Asylum-seekers who are willing to work in these industries as illegal and low-wage labor without proper work permits have a lower income level, and they also have a lower level of education and training, all of which are factors that may raise their likelihood of committing criminal acts. Employment in unregistered jobs that are not sustainable at a level that can only meet daily needs, exposure to practices that may cause unfair competition, and prejudiced approaches to

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places opened and operated by asylum seekers are some of the factors that may affect the quality of crimes that asylum seekers may commit. [Citation needed]

It is necessary to develop and execute policies with several facets to bring the social acceptance and adaption process of Syrian asylum-seekers to the appropriate levels and to assure its continuation later. These policies need to be created and implemented. Instead of receiving social assistance from the government, asylum-seekers should be encouraged to work in the appropriate fields that are needed in the labor market according to their own qualifications. This will allow them to maintain their lives and integrate into the region where they settle more easily (Yildirimalp et al., 2017: 123).

When examining the process of harmonization for Syrians, it is evident that social and cultural cohesion can be achieved in some manner; however, the most significant obstacle is their capacity to participate in economic life, to start a business, and to access the right to work, which is required for them to be able to live without being dependent on the livelihoods of others. Asylum-seekers need to get right into the business world as soon as possible if they want to be successful in overcoming one of the most significant challenges they face: the inability to make ends meet.

The Temporary Protected Status Reform and Worker Protection Act of 2016 (RWPTP) gave temporarily protected foreign nationals the authority to seek for work permits, allowing them to lawfully engage in the labor market. The RWPTP has become an urgently required stage of integration since it enables asylum-seekers to formally work for an employer or independently. This is a significant step toward easing Syrians' access to the labor market and avoiding their exploitation via registered employment. Those who are eligible for temporary protection and will be working as employees reliant on an employer and those who will be working independently in their own company are subject to various requirements when it comes to the application process for a work permit in the RWPTP. According to the latest data that was made public in 2019, the number of Syrian refugees who were issued work permits was 31,185.

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It is essential for people seeking asylum who have a variety of professions to be able to get access to working life by legal methods, to devote their time and energy to their job, to generate revenue through authorized means, and to maintain social order and cohesiveness.

During the process of putting in place programs that will assist asylum-seekers in adapting to their new environments, the "participation in production" approach should be prioritized, and state facilities should be utilized for the purposes of acquiring professions and skills, finding employment, and starting businesses (Tastan et al., 2017: 52).

According to Akcicek (2015), economic motive has a considerable influence on social acceptance and adaption processes, and it also determines a significant portion of social integration. [Citation needed] For instance, two parties that hold prejudices against one another working together under the terms of a mutual labor contract, attempting to understand one another, getting to know one another through communication, and ultimately breaking their prejudices has the effect of facilitating social cohesion (Akcicek, 2015: 60). If asylum-seekers find jobs where they can make enough money to support themselves, not only will they have a better chance of overcoming their acculturation challenges more quickly, but they will also be less likely to cause disturbances in the social order. If Syrians, who are attempting to subsist without being reliant on anyone else, are unable to find employment in Turkey or if businesses exploit them by forcing them to work for extremely low salaries, the possibility for a decline in public order and security in the nation will rise.

The Language of Media

It is crucial and vital for comprehending the present scenario that the visual and print media in Turkey have a certain attitude toward Syrians in Turkey. This attitude will facilitate societal acceptance and harmonization, as well as the development of a culture of peaceful coexistence (Erdogan et al., 2017: 12).

In terms of the media's labeling and marginalization of groups that do not fit into society and the creation of crime waves, Stanley Cohen's concept of "moral panic" is also quite important (Yildiz & Sümer, 2011: 36). Cohen made the first systematic applied study of the media's exaggeration of deviancy and the subsequent public reactions. Cohen also made the first systematic applied study of the media's exaggeration of deviancy and the subsequent public reactions. Broadcasting about Syrian asylum-seekers exclusively in terms of issues, violence, and begging has helped to the impression of Syrians as a source of worry that breaks order. This perception has also contributed to the formation of the opposition between "we" and "them." The amplification of small differences and debates among Syrians and their coverage in the press more so than their actual importance as news leads to difficulties that are difficult to deal with and the establishment of attitudes that exclude members of the society. The shoddy presentation of such judicial news in the media, together with the absence of information and the disinformation that is spread in the news, leads to manipulation and a heightened impression of a danger among the local community (Erdogan et al., 2017: 23). With the help of foreign media, the Turkish people have developed and established attitudes that are negative, discriminatory, and hostile toward asylum-seekers. These attitudes stem from the news that fights between Syrian asylum-seekers and local people that resulted in deaths and news about the granting of Turkish citizenship to Syrians to increase the reaction of the local people to immigrants (Korkmaz, 2016: 96).

It is very necessary for the media to take an active part to finish the process of integrating asylum-seekers into the society of the host country with the fewest possible complications and to preserve good migration management. Since there is a lack of reciprocal communication between the two societies, the process of social acceptance and adaptation is hampered. This is because the two civilizations have distinct cultural frameworks, behavioral patterns, and value judgements.

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The establishment of public opinion on asylum seekers and migrants is largely dependent on the role that the media plays in the discussion of these topics. The use of accusatory language in national and local publications has a significant impact on the effectiveness of migration and refugee policies that can be established now and, in the future, as well as on the likelihood of experiencing significant developments. Giving positive messages instead of using accusatory language in publications has a significant impact on determining the effectiveness of migration and refugee policies. Xenophobia, threatening speech, overblown language, and suspicions expressed in the media will unavoidably lead to an inaccurate and skewed view in society (Benoit & Benoit, 2008: 45).

The media, while reflecting its stance on the problem of migration, should be mindful of the fact that each news to be released on this topic shapes the dialogues between people and affects social peace and social order, and they should be as sensitive as is humanly feasible. When considering the resources at its disposal, it is imperative that it give credence to publications that have the potential to contribute to the growth and progression of cohesion through the production of news and programs that are helpful and supportive both in the formulation of effective migration and asylum-seeker policies by decision-makers and in the modification of the public's negative attitude toward immigrants.

The national and local newspapers, social media, radio and television broadcasts, and other forms of media must provide news on asylum-seekers with a high level of sensitivity to prevent causing tension in society. Not only will publications that may cause the stigmatization and marginalization of asylum-seekers and provocative equivocation that manipulate the masses increase the polarization between these two societies who live together but do not fully know each other, but they will also carry mutual relations to a more problematic dimension. The portrayal of Syrians as unwanted in the eyes of the entire society misleads the portion of society that is ignorant about asylum-seekers. Broadcasts that feed the prejudices and concerns of the society, discourses that characterize asylum-seekers with disorderly criminal acts Separate the two societies from each other, while discourses that characterize asylum-seekers with disorderly criminal acts

A culture of coexistence is not created when Syrians are brought to the national agenda by continually associating them with violent incidents in the media. This not only leads the local population to perceive asylum-seekers as having high criminal tendencies in a way that is both false and untrue, but it also directs the fear of crime in the society towards migrants. This is a vicious cycle that does not create a culture of coexistence. The coverage of migrants in both the visual and print media should place a greater emphasis on the humanitarian aspect of migration as well as the challenges encountered by the group that is moving to Turkey throughout the process of migration. Migration should be portrayed in the media not as a "problem," "violence," "threat," and "danger," but rather as a "manageable" concept that can "contribute" to the society that it is living in (İrdem, 2018: 211). This will help people understand the current situation and make it easier for people to live together in an atmosphere that is peaceful and tranquil.

Social and Cultural Integration

There is a definite procedure that must be followed to find a solution to the issues of social acceptability and adaption that develop as a result of migration in today's society. Many studies on the topic of migration have led researchers to the conclusion that economic and political factors are behind migration, and that movement for these reasons is largely mass rather than individual. It may take a long time for the local society to embrace mass migration, and in certain situations, it may result in the marginalization of people who move. According to Gücüten and Cereci (2021: 28), the local community may point to the fact that migrants are willing to work as a cheap labor force for low salaries in the markets of their destination as a cause for their dislike of migrants and their inability to adapt to their presence in the town.

It is not always simple for migrants who are attempting to construct a new life for themselves because of migration, nor does the process of social distinction and change necessarily end in confrontation with the inhabitants of the new location. One of the primary factors that contributes to adaptation not always being successful is the attempts made by migrants to remain faithful to the routines they developed in their country of origin and to repeat those routines in the location to which they relocated. The actions of migrants, which

lead to the stigmatization and criminalization of those migrants by the natives, are part of the process that is known as culture clash (Alpman & Yarci, 2018: 148).

Migrants may have more criminal inclinations because of the myriad of circumstances that come into play throughout the process of adjusting to and integrating themselves into the new communities in which they settle. Migrants, whose spiritual existence is more exhausted than their bodies during the migration process, and who go through a period that is psychologically traumatic, may tend to commit crimes for a variety of reasons. This is because their bodies are more physically exhausted than their spirits (Bell, 2014: 9). Migrants who bring the cultural values they have learnt and brought with them to the regions they move to are not readily absorbed by the locals and may experience responses such as humiliation if they bring those cultural values with them. It is possible for migrants, most of whom suffer with poverty after migrating, to enhance the condition of migrants resorting to crime (Gütüten & Cereci, 2021: 26). On the one hand, migrants face circumstances such as marginalization and racism. On the other hand, migrants struggle with poverty.

It has been noticed that those seeking refuge in Syria come in a variety of subgroups that are distinct not only in terms of their religious beliefs and ethnic backgrounds but also in terms of the ideologies that they adhere to. Even within groups of Syrian refugees seeking asylum, there is a significant amount of distance created due to the presence of various religious identities and ethnic origins, sexist standards, variety in culinary culture, clothes, and civic awareness. 210 As it became clear that Syrians, who were initially seen as guests by locals when they arrived in Turkey, were meant to be arrived permanent and would not return, locals began to emphasize the differences between the two communities. Initially, Syrians were seen as guests by locals when they arrived in Turkey. The negative attitude towards Syrians, the overreactions of the Turkish people that exceeded a certain limit, and the labeling of immigrants as responsible for the negative experiences that have been experienced in the society open the door to an environment that may pose a threat to both communities. The local population's unease in its relationship with Syrians, the preconceived notion that Syrians upset the balance and order of society, and the unfavorable interpersonal contact and interaction all contributed to the formation of an anti-Syrian stance.

According to the findings of the research project titled "Syrians Barometer-2019: The Framework of Living in Harmony," the initial support of the Turkish public for Syrians has significantly decreased, and the research indicates that the Turkish public's concerns about Syrians have increased as time has passed. The findings also suggest that Syrians' expectations and desires to return have reduced, and that their inclination to remain in Turkey has risen, because of the continuous conflict and instability in their country. This may be attributed to the fact that Syria is now experiencing both. The barometer reveals that Turkish society has a bad perception of Syrians, is anxious about their shared future, and maintains a cold attitude toward them.

It is possible for Syrians to feel excluded from society and angry at locals because of the bad attitude held toward them by the local population and the media, the inequalities they encounter in economic and social sectors, and the sense of exclusion they have because of these factors. It is possible that a weakening of social control and an increase in the tendency of migrants to get engaged in criminal activity might result from a failure to overcome difficulties with social adaptation and a constant growth in the number of local responses.

Conclusion And Recommendations

The moral knowledge, cultural teachings, and teachings that evolve based on personal and societal distinctions produce unique identities of civilizations, and the idea of belonging that comes along with such conditions. Migration is the beginning of a challenging process in which individuals must separate themselves from the physical environment in which they live, the social relations and economic opportunities that they are accustomed to and attempt to establish order in a society that has a different structure than the ones they are accustomed to in their new living spaces. This process can be difficult because individuals must separate themselves from the physical geography in which they live.

Migration movements have a variety of effects, both individually and collectively, on the people and the place involved. While looking at the nature, scope, and working procedure of each migration event together, one can see that each one has its own distinct components. As a result of the bloody civil war in Syria, which has been ongoing for more than a decade as a

direct result of the reflection of the social movements in Arab countries on Syria, millions of Syrians have fled the country and settled in many different countries, with Turkey being one of the most popular destinations. Turkey has become the nation that has absorbed the most Syrian refugees of any other country in the world because of its selfless response to the humanitarian disaster in Syria, which consisted of opening its doors to those seeking sanctuary. The first wave of Syrians fleeing the civil conflict that coincided with the beginning of anti-government demonstrations began on April 29, 2011, when a group of 252 individuals entered Turkey via the Cilvegözü border crossing. The number of refugees has steadily increased over the last several years. Although it was attempted to apply short-term policies to asylum-seekers who came to Turkey, considering these policies to be temporary at the beginning, the authorities ultimately decided to officially place Syrians under temporary protection with the Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP), which went into effect in 2014. This law was passed in 2014.

As a result of the conflict in Syria, Turkey has seen the greatest migration in both its own history and the history of the globe. As a result of its humanitarian open-door policy, Turkey has accommodated millions of mass migrants without imposing any criterion on their admission. Turkey, which was caught off guard by the rapid and intense mass migration, admitted those fleeing the civil conflict with the status of guest-transient without creating a policy. This was done because Turkey was caught unprepared for the sudden and intense mass migration. In the beginning, Turkey had difficulty formulating a policy regarding this matter, and it did not receive the support from the international community that it had anticipated. As a result, the country attempted to solve the issues that arose because of migration by dispersing them over a certain amount of time using its limited expertise.

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